
Research

Critical analysis of the purchasing power and behavior of consumers in marketing management

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Abstract: To design a product or service that satisfies a customer's needs, producers must first understand their wants and needs. Besides that, it is also essential to know what makes consumers choose one thing over another. When you know a customer's personality and the environment in which they work, it's easier to change their behavior and help them make good purchases. In a business setting, consumer behavior refers to how an individual responds. Research on customer behavior is a wide-ranging endeavor. It aims to connect with people deeper using primary needs, psychology, emotions, and feelings. An analysis of the client's behavior determines how a customer responds to a set of stimuli that support the relationship with him. We need to know what makes customers buy in-store or online, what makes them feel, and how they react and act. What factors influence a customer's decision to use one company's goods or services over another? The answer to this issue is not immediately apparent. When finding the best deal, rational logic does not always apply to consumer behavior. Many other things come into play concerning how people think, feel, and act. A critical analysis was carried out on consumer behavior and their purchasing power using the "people-product-situation" approach, in which several factors were considered. Internal and external factors are the primary categories used to categorize the influences on consumer decisions. Internal considerations influence the consumer's unique decision-making process; consumer needs, motivation, personality, and perception are the vital factors. A variety of external influences can influence an individual's decisions; social, economic, and cultural forces are important factors. From these research findings, the result showed that certain specific requirements, consumer activities, the purchasing process, internal and external factors, and consumer roles are critical factors in various forms and have significant influence on consumer choices, which is very important for marketing management. Therefore, understanding what makes people buy, use, or stop using a product or service helps companies better meet their needs, improve the customer's experience, boost sales, and strengthen the overall marketing management system for the organization.

Keywords: marketing management, consumer, customer involvement, methods, service, design.

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Accepted: 30 July, 2022; **Published:** 19 November, 2022

How to cite this article: DOSSA Jean-Tychique S Gbeliho, Oscar Chijioke Nkwazema, Ibrahim SANGARE, Jervis Owusu ANSAH, Sakinatu ISSAKA, Guy Herve Germain SONAN, Melaine Emmanuel KOUAME, Mariama JANNEH, Ketsia Kindja MATETU, Marie-Elisabeth GNAHOUA (2022). End-user participation in the conceptualization, planning, design, and development of marketing processes. *North American Academic Research*, 5(7), 195-217. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7338288>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Why does it matter to investigate how and why people use products and services? According to socio-demographic features of customers, is it not enough to characterize a market? If consumers have ever wondered how to advertise anything, the solution is right in front of them. In order to design a product that addresses a particular demand or position a product for a specific market group, the manager must recognize and understand the wants of customers, which is a crucial function of marketing. Although this principle is easy to comprehend, putting it into practice may be challenging. A business owner needs to have a clear idea of his target market and why they are interested in his product or service before he can position it correctly.

Marketers' ultimate goal is to sway the buyer, but before they can do that, they must first analyze, explain, and forecast the buyer's behavior. Consumer behavior research is not a perfect science. However, psychologists and sociologists need to figure out how customers are affected by psychological or social factors. Using or consuming a product is what we call being a consumer. It is not always the case that the customer is the buyer or the decision-maker and when making marketing decisions, it is critical to keep this in mind (Howard and Sheth, 1969). The consumer behavior is seen as an organism's reaction to marketing and environmental stimuli (SOR model) processed in a black box with external effects (Albert Mehrabian and James A. Russel, 1974). It is still a mystery how it works. According to this study's examination of consumer behavior, consumers always make choices based on a specific amount of information. Internal information includes things like life experiences, preferences, predispositions, and attitudes, whereas external information comes from the environment (nature of the product offered, advertising, what others say about it). Consumers considering purchasing a new laser reader will rely on their own experiences (if any) and the information offered by specialist periodicals, advertising, or the counsel of friends when making a selection. Marketing can only be successful when an organization knows the nature of the information customers use and how this information is viewed and used; these processes knowing as decision-making. Three primary forms of data impact these processes: those linked to customers, the purchasing scenario, and those related to the items. The fundamental triad consists of these three categories of variables. Hence, a significant emphasis placing on the study's analysis of consumer choice processes and the many kinds of information processing they are likely to utilize.

To begin, we will examine the fundamental triad of the "person," "central decision-making processes," "motivation," and "product scenario," all of which influence a consumer's desire to acquire a product. We will next examine the elements associated with the purchasing situation. Before making a purchase, customers need to think about their information and decide what to do.

Research methodology

1. People - Product - Situation: The basic triad

The basic triangle of people-product-situation is a foundational notion in studying consumer behavior. This concept states that we cannot comprehend the dynamics of a market or even a specific sector of this market without examining the customer, the product he or she purchases, and the context in which this purchase occurs. Can consumer behavior's depth and complexity only be discovered in this manner? In order to keep existing customers or attract new ones who share similar sensibilities, a business owner will need to attract and maintain a devoted following. As an alternative,

consumers are more likely to make purchases based on their place in society. The product will play a less critical role in the marketing strategy than the means through which it is distributed and how information is exchanged around it (Robertson et al., 2014).

Consumers' decision-making processes and criteria must be considered to comprehend their actions properly and why they do so. This is because these processes can only be described if we consider all of these factors together. We must consider them while attempting to understand them.

In order to successfully influence customer behavior in a manner that benefits the organization, the study of demand encompasses not only the observation of behavior but also the explanations and understandings that go along with it. Two statements are particularly relevant among the ECC definitions. The first one brings consumer behavior research closer to looking at the different things people do to buy or get a product or service in response to a need. The second, proposed by (Engel, Kollat, and Blackwell, 2016), is centered on individual activities in connection to purchasing but constantly incorporates decision-making procedures that favor these actions. Consumer behavior research is an essential component of the marketing process. The aspects of relevant consumer behavior encompass developing a study of relevant consumer behavior by studying requirements and motives, as well as the numerous procedures preceding the purchase. ECC employs marketing by keeping an eye on:

- understand the consumer's requirements, tastes, and habits;
- communicate, entice, seduce, or generate demand
- Where should I sell?

2. What are we Studying in consumer behavior?

In the examination of consumer behavior, several factors are considered. We uncover specific needs and goals, internal and external factors, consumer activities, the buying process, and the different roles a consumer might play (buyer, payer, prescriber, or user), among other things.

Figure 1: Basic model of Consumer Behavior

a. Stimuli

A stimulus is "the convergence of a need and an element capable of satisfying it". Three sorts of variables may influence a customer's view of whether or not an offer's feature is likely to satisfy an unmet need:

- The products and their physical or symbolic characteristics (attributes).
- Interpersonal communication (contacts with others, observing other people's behaviors).
- Commercial communications (advertisements, sellers' arguments).

b. Integrations and decision-making variables

The four fundamental processes

It is via this process that the consumer may both become aware of his surroundings and make sense of the data he receives:

- The perception process allows the consumer, on the one hand, become aware of his environment and, on the other hand, interpret the information receives.
- The memorization process is at the origin of the storage and use of the information received by the consumer.
- The learning process allows the consumer to acquire experiences that explain, for example, consumer habits.
- The other information processing processes are involved in forming consumer attitudes towards the products and services surrounding them.

Figure 2 : Decision making process

c. The internal states of the consumer

Motivations are "internal states that push the individual towards a behavior or an action".

Figure 3 : Consumer internal states

The responses

They are a mirror of what the public desires. There are two types of responses: purchase or non-purchase of a product or brand, and mode of consumption or usage of that product or brand.

Empirical evidence is more common than stimuli and decisions regarding consumer reactions.

Feedback

People's choices and actions are influenced by their prior actions. The impact of these previous encounters is expressed in the form of feedback.

Variables that explain

They are grouped into two main categories:

- a) Individual characteristics are the primary source of explanation for the variations in behavior seen between people. A distinction is made between the consumer's sociodemographic characteristics, psychological characteristics, and psychographic (or psycho-social) characteristics. In the consumer's environment, distinct, more or less institutionalized groups shape the environment.
- b) Characteristics relating to the environment: the consumer's environment is structured by the existence of different, more or less formalized groups. We make a difference between the culture of the person's home country, social class, the groups they belong to or refer to, and their family.

As part of our research study, we focus our study on the analysis of five individual variables: the consumer's involvement with the products offered; his degree of experience in using these products; his sociodemographic characteristics; his personality; and finally, the benefits he is looking for in a product.

d. Involvement

The degree of participation in a product is by far the most significant consumer-related characteristic. The phrase "importance" or "personal interest" connected with a product in a specific context has been defined in many ways by the researchers who have studied it throughout time and across different study streams; there seems to be unanimity on this point. (Rothschild's, 2016) concept of participation is as follows: motivation, stimulus, or interest are all examples of involvement. Current external factors and previous internal variables determine this state's process. Consequently, multiple methods of gathering, analyzing, and making decisions are used. It is reasonable to interpret participation as a measure of how important a specific product is to a particular person in that scenario. In this case, a term that is both structural and conjunctural (i.e. situation-related) is utilized. While one client may always view automobiles as an engaging product, another may only feel this way in certain situations. There are many factors that contribute to customer involvement, but they all boil down to the consumer's perception of risk and interest in the product or service category in which they're purchasing or using. Another way to look at it is that users are more inclined to use a product that they see as risky. There are several dangers associated with alcohol consumption. Each threat may exist independently of the others; they are not mutually exclusive. Function, economic, psychological, and social hazards are the most important factors influencing a consumer's decision to buy a product or service. One of the most significant influences on consumer behavior is operational risk. It may be characterized as the risk of having the product fail to meet expectations. Personal-use items, such as medications, dyes, cosmetics, and services provided by a doctor, a dentist, or a lawyer, are especially vulnerable to this danger. The customer has two options when it comes to minimizing the operational risk. For example, the shopper might strive to learn everything he can about a specific product or service before making a final decision. When lowering one's operational risk, consumers may rely on anything from online reviews and advertisements to word-of-mouth recommendations from friends. It is also possible to lower one's operational risk by placing a wager on "certain values." In other words, since they have specific values, such as the newest Spielberg film, the best-selling beer, or the brand of an automobile they currently own, many customers do not need a lengthy decision-making process to make these purchases. These examples demonstrate how operational risk affects the decision-making process when it is present. As a first step, the customer will seek out further information to help mitigate the risk. To put it another way, a customer already familiar with particular values will not face a high functional risk in the second situation and will not need to gather as much information. In other words, consumers are more likely to choose a method of decision-making that reduces risk if they perceive the risk as more significant.

Economic risk is the easiest kind of risk to comprehend. More decision-making will be involved in buying expensive goods in this situation. Of course, a consumer's ability to pay will significantly impact this connection. The danger to the economy doesn't just come from the price of the goods themselves; it could also come from other costs, like shipping fees, accessories, and other options.

Psychological risk is the danger that purchase or consumption will not align with the consumer's ideal self-image. As a result, a moviegoer could avoid violent scenes out of dread for his subconscious, or a hockey fan might avoid going since he is no longer in excellent physical condition. Decision-making processes get more complicated when consumers are exposed to psychological risk.

However, the social risk is more a result of how others see us than how we perceive ourselves. Some individuals need to style their hair in a specific manner to be a member of a particular peer group rather than for personal preference. On the other hand, other customers may avoid participating in particular pastimes out of fear of being assessed negatively by their friends or coworkers. There is, of course, a danger that not all customers face. People only pose a risk to others when their use is obvious and they are aware of their surroundings.

e. The experience

As with engagement, the complexity of a consumer's decision-making process is greatly influenced by their experience with a product. His decision-making process will be quicker if he has experience. Some consumers have become "experts" on the product due to their extensive use of it. Whether it is a brand of car, a laundry service, or the services of a dental surgeon, a consumer's past experiences will influence his decision-making process. When a customer has used a particular brand for a long time, he or she will only consider that brand when making a purchase. When a customer considers several options, the knowledge they gain will help them choose by showing them the proper criteria to use and the right way to judge them.

Customers categorize their experiences to build subsets of possibilities that they accept or reject based on what they know or do not know about them.

Consumers are more likely to act on their beliefs that they would get excellent value from an item if their experience with it is both good and acceptable, and when this happens, a solid emotional predisposition is created in them. This helps to explain why so many individuals are loyal to a single brand or product. After discussing how people make decisions and their views, we shall return to these emotional predispositions.

f. Sociodemographic characteristics

Sociodemographic traits are among the most well-known elements that might impact decision-making processes. Gender, age, and the family life cycle all have a non-negligible impact on consumer behavior. The intensity of perceived risks and the level of experience are both influenced by these sociodemographic variables, which in turn are influenced by income (age is a determining factor of experience). Even when the sociodemographic variables are correct, it is often necessary to go beyond them to explain why customers choose certain products or services.

g. Personalities

Personality is one of the most intriguing characteristics in the study of consumer behavior, but it is also one of the most inconclusive. As a result, we would like to think that a person with this personality would prefer rock music while another would prefer opera, or that some consumers have specific values in mind while others are looking for something new and different. While these theories may be intriguing conceptually, practical evidence seldom supports them. Despite this, even though personality qualities do not entirely explain consumer behavior, some of these features are interesting to look into. As a result, some customers act on their predispositions, while others act on the expectations of their peers. This personality trait significantly affects how people see social risk and, as a result, the decisions they make in their daily lives.

3.0 Potential advantages

Tennis rackets come in various shapes, sizes, and price points, and customers may use them for various reasons, from exoticism to relaxation to performance and pricing. The advantages sought will have a significant impact on the kind of decision-making process employed for many items. Consumers who are torn between two or more brands might decide by comparing them. Based on each racket's qualities, their capacity to offer the appropriate level of enjoyment might be determined. We will go back to this specific example when we cover the many decision-making methods. There is no one-size-fits-all answer regarding the advantages of utilizing a product. Put another way, the hoped-for advantages are strongly tied to the operational risk.

For managers, the notion of benefits sought may help them better understand and use consumer decision-making processes and the parts of the commercial composition. As long as customers base their decisions on the advantages they want, analyzing the benefits desired by consumers is acceptable. There are times when this "search for rewards" isn't essential, as we shall see later. Consumers, on the other hand, are frequently unable to describe why a product or service is excellent. Customers are more likely to evaluate a product's or service's advantages when they invest more in the product or service. Consumers must have the knowledge and time to use these features.

4.0 Factors influencing behavior

Two main categories of factors:

- ▶ Individual factors
- ▶ Environmental factors

Figure 4 : Factors influencing behavior

Figure 5: Individual factors

Figure 6 : Buying reason (Environmental factors)

5.0 Motivation

5.1 Definition and explanation

This term refers to all the factors or needs that determine behavior. Motivation is linked to two aspects of behavior. Behavior is the total of all the causes or requirements that influence a person's actions. For this reason, it is focused on meeting their demands. If we want to understand consumer behavior, we need to remember that people will only purchase what they are interested in. Although it may sound like a typical statement, too many managers forget it, which causes them to be frustrated. Consumers' actions are sparked by their intrinsic drives, called "motivation." An imbalance between a consumer's present and intended state is at the root of this problem. The more of an imbalance there is, the more likely the customer is to take action. For example, as a consumer ages, he may feel the need to read poetry or have more free time to spend on leisure activities. This imbalance may also result from a specific circumstance (around 6 p.m., food shoppers are more likely to make impulse purchases) or the promotion of a product by a company (sales and discounts offered by companies aim to accelerate an expenditure that would have occurred otherwise). However, contrary to common assumptions, consumers cannot be influenced by any stimuli, regardless of the forces being

presented to them. If he has had positive experiences with the product or brand in the past, he will be more likely to be motivated by it in the future. In turn, these two factors will significantly influence the decision-making process. Because of this, the decision-making process will differ for each product or service depending on the components of our three-component triad: person, product, and scenario. As a matter of fact, in most circumstances, the complexity of decision-making processes and the amount of information processing are strongly linked in most cases. Consumers are more likely to employ a wide range of information if their decision-making process is more difficult to understand. When a customer is motivated and his decision-making process is more complicated, marketing managers need to know this since it signals that their commercial content will be scrutinized more carefully. A company's marketing manager, for example, may be worried about a customer's reluctance to absorb too much information. Providing as much information as possible may be desirable if a company wants its customers to fully grasp the benefits of its product over those of its competitors. In this circumstance, consumer motivation becomes a valuable asset if it exists.

The interdependence of our core trio of elements is seen in the motivation and complexity of consumer decision-making. Starting with the unique qualities of each customer, we will look at the many other factors that contribute to the success of a business.

5.2 The process and buying motivations

When a person's needs are met, their motivation begins to flow. There are two types of these:

Biogenic: is created by a physiological imbalance such as a lack of air, water, etc.

Psychogenic: resulting from human interaction with their social and cultural surroundings (desire to look good, to have prestige, affection).

Buying anything is a way to fulfill a want or a need. People buy on the basis of their ideas, feelings, emotions, and intuition. The following is a breakdown of the most common reasons people buy:

a. Emotional purchases:

An emotional buy is one in which no consideration of logic or rationality is given before making a purchase. In this situation, the consumer is impacted by their emotions. Here are a few illustrations:

- When making a purchase, most people are motivated by a sense of pride. For many purchasers, owning a product is a source of pride. Marketers use pride and distinction as selling points for a variety of items. Buying diamonds from a jeweler, for example, may raise a person's social position to the pinnacle. The act of following in the footsteps of someone or striving to outdo them is known as an imitation. Many people want an iPhone simply because their coworkers have one.
- Buying a product because you want to feel at home is another common emotional motive for doing so. The convenience that a product offers is a major selling point. Ventilation, microwaves, household appliances, mattresses, etc. are just a few examples. All of these products are purchased by consumers because of the convenience they provide.

b. Reasonable purchases

Purchasing products in this sector is usually the result of much deliberation. There are several reasons to purchase:

- This need for safety may be a strong motivator for purchasing a product. People acquire steel safes and security lockers, for example, in order to safeguard all of their cash and valuables. In the same way, we take nutritional supplements and other dietary supplements to prevent illness,
- Consumers' behavior is strongly influenced by value, which is why it is essential to keep prices low. Most consumers compare the prices of similar goods before making a purchase, and they nearly always go with the

lowest option. At least once every two weeks, a marketing message keeps them interested in their business product or service.

5.3 Purchase process

Several tracks and, ultimately, the sound quality are the factors that a buyer considers while deciding between Sony, Sharp, Koss, and G.E. portable audio systems. A customer could choose the best option logically and objectively if they assigned a weight to each quality based on how important it is to them.

a. Situational factors

The situations in which the consumer makes his purchases have constituted clear progress in understanding his behavior. We call a situation "a set of factors related to a given time and place which, without finding their origin in the stable characteristics of people or products, exert a manifest influence on behavior." Five dimensions to characterize the situational context:

- The physical environment (such as location, and temperature.).
- The social environment (such as the presence or absence of other people, such as children).
- The time
- The reason for the purchase (purchasing for oneself, purchasing as a gift, etc.).
- The consumer's initial state (i.e., the consumer's state of mind or mood at the start of the situation).

c. The stages of the process: The Principles of Decision-Making

In light of the numerous aspects we've observed, we may now conduct a study of the various sorts of decision-making strategies that might explain why consumers choose to purchase or consume a certain product. Keeping this in mind, managers must be aware of these procedures since it's via these processes that customers will assess the numerous items that a manager has to provide. Understanding these processes can help them develop more effective marketing strategies. The key decision-making procedures are shown in the following diagram, along with some of the differences between them.

Figure 7 : Principle of decision-making

i. Attitude

Familiarity and involvement with a product or category are critical factors in this decision-making process. For this kind of procedure to take place, the product must have a significant effect on the consumer's attitude, as well as a favorable social backdrop and a personality that allows this attitude to be taken into account in the purchasing process. Attitude is a powerful mechanism that allows consumers to make judgments fast, promptly, and successfully based on their outstanding experiences and the confidence in their judgment that arises from them. An organization, brand, or store that benefits from a customer's positive attitude is a fantastic asset since it represents a decision-making process that is particularly tough to modify. This method is also known as the "learned attitude" effect; it is beneficial to the organization that uses it while creating an obstacle for others. The reason for the attitude mechanism's lifetime is that it

has a direct effect on the person who owns it. If people have ideas about how a product is seen as a whole, they might also have ideas about how it is made.

We must first understand how behavior is influenced to understand how it impacts buyer decision-making. The majority of attitudes are shaped by life events, which, as we shall see later, might result from an unconstrained, cognitive, or dynamic process. These processes are often a mix of many categories. In many instances, however, an attitude may be attributed to an obscure learning process (e.g., why does a customer dislike the color yellow?). One of these methods is classical conditioning, through which a neutral stimulus gets an emotional charge when linked with a stimulus with an affective charge. This notion is commonly used in advertising. It is especially true when a well-known celebrity endorses a product. When a connection is created between an emotionally charged star and a neutral stimulus, the neutral stimulus is more likely to be selected.

ii. Cognitive Processes

In the case of items with a high level of participation, the customer is more likely to follow cognitive decision-making processes even if he has little product-use experience. These lengthier and more intricate procedures examine different product qualities. To comprehend what cognitive processes are, examine the following illustration. A customer is on the fence between four brands of portable audio systems: Sony, Sharp, Koss, and General Electric. By rating each quality based on its value to her and assessing each option based on these traits, our customer could objectively and logically choose the best option. This strategy, partly created by psychologists (Martin Fishbein, 2016), is known as the compensatory linear model of decision-making in marketing. As the chart below demonstrates, this decision-making approach requires a detailed and specific procedure.

Table 1 : Cognitive process analysis

	COMPETITIVE PRICE	GUARANTEE	TECHNOLOGY QUALITY	SOUND QUALITY
IMPORTANCE	4	3	1	1
SONY	1	3	3	5
SHARP	1	3	5	3
KOSS	4	3	3	3
G.E	4	3	3	3

RATINGS LEGEND: 1 = unimportant - very bad; 5 = very important - very good.

If our consumer applies such a decision-making process, then her decision will be formulated as follows:

$$M_j = \sum I_{ij} \times E_{ij}$$

M_j = evaluation of brand j

i = number of criteria evaluated

I_{ij} = importance of criterion i for brand j

E_{ij} = evaluation of criterion I for brand j

In the case of a compensatory linear model, the choice that will be retained will be the one that will maximize the value of Mj. In the present case, the results obtained by applying the model are the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SONY} &= (4*1) + (3*3) + (1*3) + (3*5) = 31 \\ \text{SHARP} &= (4*1) + (3*3) + (1*5) + (3*3) = 27 \\ \text{KOSS} &= (4*4) + (3*3) + (1*3) + (3*4) = 40 \\ \text{G.E.} &= (4*4) + (3*3) + (1*3) + (3*3) = 37 \end{aligned}$$

According to these results, our consumers should choose the Koss brand. This choice is explained mainly by the optimal combination of a price deemed adequate and sound quality. It should be noted that the guarantee ultimately played no part in this process since all the manufacturers considered offered a guarantee deemed to be equivalent. Like the compensatory linear model, the connective model seeks to characterize the structure of consumer decision-making processes. The customer establishes an acceptable minimum threshold for each criterion in this concept. If a candidate fails to meet this criterion, he or she is instantly dismissed. Consequently, if a tennis racquet must be constructed of graphite for a customer, any wooden or aluminum racquet, regardless of its quality or price, will be dismissed. It might be of the utmost significance for a manager to understand that most targeted customers follow a conjunctive rather than a compensating linear model. Camping equipment manufacturers may try to alter the decision-making process or even the pricing of their products if they know that a substantial number of prospective customers adopt the connected model and that more than \$100 for a traveler's tent will dissuade them from purchasing it. Assuming the first experiment works out, he will make a case for compensating linear pricing by pointing out the need to invest a bit more money on higher-quality materials, such as a lighter frame and a more durable field. However, as customer decision-making processes are often challenging to alter, the manager may choose to change his pricing or give this clientele a product of lesser quality, thus broadening his product line. It is crucial to highlight that decision-making processes are seldom totally compensatory, entirely connective, or even wholly of another kind; most decision-making processes are hybrid. Thus, it is relatively rare for a customer to begin his decision-making process with a conjunctive model to exclude some options, followed by a compensating linear model to arrive at his ultimate selection. For a manager tasked with addressing a particular customer, the determination and comprehension of these procedures represent a strong lever. The marketing manager may then change parts of his commercial to reflect what customers want and how important those things are to them.

A manager can only benefit from knowing sophisticated cognitive processes to the degree that customers employ them. However, it is noteworthy that this is not always the case in particular sectors. In this sense, managers must consider subcontracted activities and dynamic processes to comprehend customer behavior. This is because some goods and services are new and creative, and some decision-making processes (like choosing a movie, a restaurant, or whether or not to jump on an elastic band) have a strong emotional component.

iii. Sub-Contracted Processes

A customer with a strong opinion on a product may employ a cognitive decision-making process due to his limited expertise with the product in question. In such situations, if the consumer lacks the talent or time to analyze all the information required to make a choice, he would often choose an outsourced decision-making process. There are three primary categories of subcontracted processes: imitation-based, recommendation-based, and deference-based (compliance). In each instance, the decision-making process (or a portion of it) is delegated to a third party. This third party must be reputable in the eyes of the customer for the system to operate. Frequently, this source of imitation or reference is a friend or family member. This is how we may explain the effect of the reference group, which, for many things with

apparent consumption (clothing, hairstyles, automobiles, etc.), will be significant in determining purchase behavior. Many customers choose to delegate the process of making decisions because of the difficulty and lack of interest they have in doing it themselves. The phenomenon also applies to a supplier on whom the buyer would depend because he cannot determine the optimal option for himself. However, for many consumers, the influence of vendors, friends, or consumerist groups will be minimal. In other instances, the provided views and ideas only show an aspect of the cognitive process (linear compensatory model, conjunctive, etc.).

iv. Positive processes

Until now, the predominant decision-making processes we have seen have portrayed the consumer as a cognitive person who examines a product's many qualities to maximize consumption. Marketers must consider other techniques, such as dynamic processes and the utilitarian paradigm that dominates the industry today. Experience, rather than objective features, is the driving force behind certain purchases, as consumers seek products that bring hedonistic pleasure. Emotions (love, hate, pleasure, boredom, weariness, etc.) play a far more significant role in decision-making than rational considerations such as weighing pros and cons. Customers of cultural products rely heavily on these decision-making systems. Since most decision-making processes involve a mix of cognitive and emotional factors, the manager must be aware of this emotional component. In such instances, gaining preferences consists of a sequence of more or less conscious encounters that induce a sense of pleasure in the consumer. For management, it is difficult to specify the parameters involved in such processes since, by definition, the customer cannot adequately describe them. Consequently, the so-called trial-and-error technique is sometimes the only viable marketing strategy for managers who target a set of customers seeking certain sorts of pleasure. This way, marketing strategy becomes closer to an art than a science.

v. The habit

"Habit is another decision-making tool for consumers. Similar to attitude, habit enables the customer to make rapid decisions. Unlike attitude, however, habit is characterized by a low-level engagement process. An illustration will help us comprehend this discrepancy. Madame X has a solid and favorable opinion of Minute Maid orange juice; she purchases it weekly. Mrs. F does the same, although with a lesser degree of commitment. Imagine a scenario in which the grocery store frequented by Ladies X and F does not carry Minute Maid. In the example of Mrs. X, we may anticipate behavior reflective of her high level of engagement with the product. She might go elsewhere for supplies, purchase nothing and wait, or choose a different brand, but only after examining the quality of the various items available. In the second instance, with Mrs. F, it is feasible that the replacement is performed in a far more mechanical manner. For the consumer, a habit is a straightforward and systematic method for selecting a product or group of items whose purchase or use entails little risk.

vi. Fortuitous purchase

Inconsequential and accidental purchases are based on this decision-making process, characterized by low participation and poor experience. In these instances, the placement of the product, the color of the container, the presence of a discount, etc., are all techniques that will increase consumption. This phenomenon is noticed in particular among video club members. For these customers, renting a tape is a low-involvement activity; hence, their decision-making process may be as easy as selecting the title that seems to be the most known among the novelties.

vii. Situation variables

As we saw at the outset of this article, the decision-making processes and associated information processing techniques are contingent on several situational aspects. The primary situational factors include the period (day, month, season, etc.) in which the purchase is made; the amount of time available to the customer to make the purchase; the existence or absence of reference groups; the economic climate; and the physical setting in which the choice is made. The purchase's timing might influence the decision-making process. According to company owners, customers' inclination to

buy products is influenced by whether or not there is snow in December. During this time of the year, the Nutcracker ballet, folk music, and fruit cake are well-known traditions. There are exceptions, however.

A customer's decision-making process is influenced by the length of time he has to choose. The client will depend more on subcontracted methods and those based on existing experience when this period is compressed. Recommendation groups may influence the decision-making process as well. The presence of a reference group or an influential person may influence a customer's decision-making process when they are faced with a difficult option.

In addition, the current economic condition has a significant impact. The client is more likely to use a cognitive decision-making process that emphasizes product pricing in times of recession or when he is more sensitive to economic circumstances. This is not the only factor influencing a customer's decision-making choices. Another essential factor to consider is whether the customer would employ mental or emotional processes depending on the presence or absence of specific mental or emotional inputs.

Figure 8 : Consumer decision-making process

5.3 Process Evaluation

a. Recognition of the problem

The acknowledgment of a need may be defined as the consumer's sense of a disparity between the desired condition and a felt state. It is plausible to assume that this disparity leads to the sense of a need only if it falls below a particular threshold. The consumer thus perceives an unsatisfying circumstance, often known as a "consumption issue." Several sorts of causes may contribute to the emergence of such a change. These substances are called "need stimulating factors."

b. Information gathering

After identifying a customer's needs, the next step is to gather information. The consumer searches his long-term memory for potential solutions to the presented situation. This is the internal search for information. The majority of the time, a customer will seek out the conduct taken before in a comparable scenario to repeat it if it resulted in pleasure or avoid it if it did not. When the consumer cannot recall this knowledge from his long-term memory, he participates in an information-gathering procedure. The information-gathering process may be classified along three dimensions: its intensity, direction, and the order of its steps. Finally, it should be highlighted that the information search process might vary significantly across consumers and between products.

c. Evaluating the potential

This third stage is fundamental. It results in constructing an opinion about a product or brand that may be positive enough for the customer to contemplate purchasing it. Discussing the qualities and brands kept by the customer throughout the decision-making process is appropriate. A class of items is associated with a consumption issue by a customer seeking a solution. It then establishes a set of qualities for this category of items, i.e., evaluation criteria likely to be used for the various brands available. There are several kinds of attributes:

Figure 9 : Potential Evaluation

A characteristic will be crucial if the customer sees substantial variations between brands at the level of that attribute and if the attribute is relevant. To make this judgment, we look at how different an aspect is between two brands that are already competing with one another.

When a customer considers a characteristic at the moment of the purchase to decide between different brands, that attribute is referred to as being "salient." When comparing one product category to another and one customer to another, it is possible to find significant variations in the buy sets employed.

5.4 How do customers create their perspectives?

Consumers form attitudes based on their evaluations of a product's or feature's capacity to meet their needs for purchase and consumption, as represented by their evaluation criteria.

Similarly, consumers can form an attitude by only seeing the ad, which means they can form attitudes toward the product. Attitudes based on direct experience are held more confidently. This means that consumers are more convinced of the product if they have direct experience with it.

Figure 10 : Customer perspectives

6.0 Typology of Purchasing Behaviors

The purchasing behavior of the individual customer is complex; he is a multiple being who can experience multiple desires simultaneously. This is why retailers must have a good knowledge of the different levels of an act of purchase to improve their marketing and merchandising strategies.

Figure 11: Type of purchasing behavior

6.1 Consumer buying behavior

Consumer buying habits are the steps consumers take (both online and offline) before purchasing a product or service. This involves researching the internet, using comparison websites, participating in consumer markets, or even using social networking sites. Businesses should take this procedure into account since it aids in developing successful marketing strategies. The buying process of a consumer includes multiple steps: desire, need, information gathering, comparisons, site selection, and payment, to name a few. Because of this, it is vital to examine all purchasers' emotional, mental, and behavioral responses during these phases. Consequently, behavioral analysis is a multi-disciplinary field that draws from economics, marketing, and psychology.

Customers' decision-making is influenced by the nature of the transaction. Buying a toothbrush, a tennis racquet, a computer, and a new car have other differences. Seller engagement and consideration will be particularly critical in complex and expensive deals.

Engagement is the degree to which an object or event has meaning to the individual who experiences it. How many customers feel connected and loyal to the product or company. Engaging the head and emotions is an essential part of participation. It is very uncommon for people to say, "I love my ancient vehicle since he never disappoints [cognition]." There are three degrees of involvement to choose from:

- ▶ If the traits are unconnected to the outcomes, there is low engagement.
- ▶ If the function is connected to the characteristics, then the implication is moderate.
- ▶ If a consumer thinks that a product's features are strongly related to their end goals or values, this will significantly affect the product.

According to research, three frequent elements boost a person's chance of becoming heavily involved in decisions. These are the ones we are referring to:

- how much you make compared to how much you spend
- duration of ownership of the acquisition
- The degree to which the purchase represents the buy.

Purchasing high-involvement goods and services is essential to the consumer's lifestyle. That is to say; they need meaningful choices to be made the first time correctly. The items with which a customer is most intimately associated are the ones about which the customer feels most strongly and about which he or she knows the most.

Involvement with a solid emotional component does not have to be expensive. Cheap things are also a big draw for many people. As a result, the cost of participation does not necessarily match the value offered. It is not necessary that a high-involvement product be expensive or that a low-involvement product be inexpensive. Due to the low cost of cigarettes, smokers may become highly invested in their brands. On the other hand, a luxurious 5-star hotel may not captivate everyone.

Based on the level of buyer participation and brand differentiation, (Assael, 2015) identified four categories of consumer purchasing behavior. The following table and the following paragraphs list and discuss each of the four categories.

Table 1 : Consumer buying behavior

	High involvement	Low involvement
Significant differences between competing brands	Complex decision	Decision marked by the search for varieties
No perceived difference between competing brands	Decision to reduce cognitive dissonance	Decision corresponding to inertia

a. Complex buying behavior

Buying behavior becomes more complicated when customers are deeply involved in the process and aware of the wide range of brand distinctions. Consumers are extremely engaged when a product is expensive, seldom bought, risky, and highly expressive. There is much information that the client needs to know about the product category in general. For example, someone shopping for a computer may be unsure of what features to prioritize. "16K.memory" is a meaningless term for most consumers, as are terms like "disk storage" and "screen resolution." This consumer will go through a learning process that includes acquiring product-related ideas and attitudes and making a conscious purchasing choice. "To successfully sell a high-engagement product, the marketer must understand how high-engagement clients gather and evaluate data. Buyers must be educated about the product class qualities, their relative importance, and how the company's brand stands out in those aspects. Using print materials and extensive language, the marketer should highlight how each brand is distinctive and urge sales associates in stores and buyers with knowledge to influence the final brand decision.

b. Buying reduces discord

When buyers are emotionally committed to a product, they may not see the difference between different brands. The purchase is expensive, rare, and hazardous based on the solid connotation. There will be a lot of comparison shopping in this case, but it will be reasonably rapid since the brand differences are not noticeable. Price or convenience may be the primary factors driving a customer's decision.

Buyers' dissonance may arise if, after acquiring a product, they find or hear clear statements about a competitor's company. Any rationale for the customer's selection will be closely scrutinized. To begin, the client must take action, form new beliefs, and adopt a new set of behaviors. In this case, marketing communications aim to elicit customers' positive feedback.

c. Habitual shopping behavior

It is not uncommon for consumers to purchase things with little thought to their chosen brand. This sort of product has nothing to do with consumers. They go to the shop to search for the mark. Choosing the same brand over and over again is a habit, not a choice based on personal preference. There are several reasons to believe that most low-cost, often purchased items are of little interest to customers. The typical patterns of consumer behavior are disrupted when this occurs. Brand research, feature comparison, and meaningful brand selection are not everyday occurrences among consumers. To gain knowledge, people watch TV or read advertisements. It is not the advertising that persuades consumers to purchase a product but their repetition. If a brand is well-known, people will select it even if they do not like it. If the goods are unimportant to them, they may forget about them after purchasing them. Following passive exposure to a brand, a person's perception of the brand is influenced by their purchasing behavior and appraisal. Marketers of items

with limited brand loyalty and little differentiation between brands discover that pricing and sales promotions effectively entice customers to test their products. A few things to keep in mind while promoting a product with minimal interest.

There should be just a few crucial things in the ad language that should be highlighted. As symbols and images are simple to recall and relate to the brand, they are crucial. Short messages should be repeated over and over again in advertising efforts. Television is more effective than print media as a low-involvement, passive learning tool. Advertisements that are well thought out should be based on the principles of classical conditioning. A customer becomes familiar with a product through this concept because of a symbol that repeatedly appears in it. A product with low engagement may be turned into a product with higher engagement by marketers. That is to say:

- Marketers may do this by connecting the product with another topic, such as when they state that Crest toothbrushes can help prevent cavities.
- Individuals can relate the product to aspects of their own life while thinking about it. An excellent illustration of this would be to advertise a particular brand of coffee first thing in the morning when the target audience is trying to get out of bed.
- Advertisements could aim to get people to have strong feelings about their egos or ideals.
- An essential component may be easily added to a product with little additional effort. One way to improve the nutritional value of a typical beverage, for instance, is by fortifying it with vitamins.

These techniques, at most, make customers less disinterested in the product and a bit more interested in it, but they do not make customers particularly interested in purchasing it.

d. Buying behavior looking for varieties

Certain purchasing circumstances are characterized by little engagement from the customer but considerable variation across brands. It is not difficult to observe that consumers often swap brands in this context. The customer adheres to a set of beliefs, selects a biscuit brand without giving it much consideration, and then contemplates those beliefs while eating the biscuit. On the other hand, if people become tired of it or want a new flavor, they could choose a different brand the next time such feelings arise. The rebranding is taking place not because customers are dissatisfied but because they are interested in trying something different. The brand that dominates this market and the lesser ones in this category each have unique marketing strategies. The company with the dominant position in the market will make an effort to entice consumers to make frequent purchases by stocking their shelves with the most incredible variety of goods, preventing unexpected runs out of inventory, and sponsoring frequent advertising campaigns. The businesses that make up the Challenger Group will run advertisements in the form of discounts, special offers, coupons, and free samples, as well as other types of advertisements that give individuals an incentive to try new items.

7.0 What is purchase management, and why is it important?

The control of an organization's inventory and the management of proper inventory stock levels are directly influenced by the purchasing choices. Good purchasing management techniques should simplify the purchasing and inventory control processes to reduce the cost of maintaining inventory and guarantee timely delivery of inventory levels. Investments in inventory goods are often made by firms that do not keep track of purchases. Stock purchases are just one part of the purchasing process. Suppliers and sources of inventory stock are vetted, and deliveries are monitored to ensure they are received on time, in acceptable shape, and in the appropriate amount.

i. What is purchase management?

As a corporate practice, purchase management allows organizations to control procurement operations' actions and relationships. Simply put, purchase management is essential to any business that sells, retails, or makes things. Efficiency in procurement management offers suppliers a great potential to increase earnings by reducing inventory

expenses. For an organization to be as productive as possible, it needs to get products and services at the best price and quality possible. Designing purchasing strategies around a single major customer is critical if you want the most significant outcomes from a single point of contact.

ii. Purchasing cycles

Before making any purchase, a company will go through a series of procedures represented by a buying cycle. The first thing that must be done is establish a need for a specific product, which is followed by figuring out how much of that product is needed and when it must be delivered. Consider the price and quality of various goods and stockpiles offered by many suppliers before determining where the items should be acquired. After that, approval is given for a purchase order. At more prominent companies, approval of a purchase order may be required from more than one individual. After that, the company and the supplier will negotiate to determine the terms of the purchase contract. Decisions on whether or not the chosen supplier will be an ongoing business partner might be made at this stage in the purchasing process. When the stock is received into the firm, the products are tallied and verified for quality before being entered into the company's inventory management system.

iii. Why does purchase management matter?

The management of purchases influences cash flow, the cost of inventory stock, contractual difficulties, and product availability. As a result, companies need to have a reliable procedure to acquire their inventory supply.

The most fundamental tenet of buy management is the need for all products and services to be acquired and provided at the most favorable prices available to maximize profits. Keeping an excessive inventory stock costs money, and it also represents an opportunity cost since the money might have been spent in other ways that would have been more beneficial.

It is essential to have effective purchase management because getting the appropriate commodities at the appropriate price and at the appropriate time is essential. Spending more than necessary on inventory for your retail or manufacturing business may have a significant negative impact on your profitability.

iv. Benefits of purchase management

A system for purchase management generates individualized approval guidelines, allowing for the acceleration of approval processes and order placement in preparation for the on-time delivery of inventory stock. Purchase management is a process that simplifies an organization's buying and inventory control procedures, resulting in increased productivity and decreased expenses. Understanding customers' behavior will help in purchase management in an organization.

v. Purchasing management solutions

The use of software to monitor and regulate the acquisition of inventory stock across many channels or for a single location may be optimized via warehouse operations when the program is used. Because everything is monitored from a single centralized place, the technologies make it easier to regulate inventories and contribute to the development of stronger relationships with suppliers. Purchasing processes may interface with one another and electronically connect your organization to data on real-time inventory stock levels.

Conclusion

From our people-product-situation analysis, we found that the decision-making process is based on a lot of factors. As a result, one of the essential responsibilities of marketing is to provide the consumer with information that may be suitable both in nature and in the structure of the decision-making process that it will follow. Naturally, the more relevant a consumer's experiences with a product or a category of products, the less they will seek information from outside sources and the less sensitive they will be to marketing solicitation. The more a consumer has relevant experience with a product or a category of products, the easier it is for them to make a buying decision.

This study's overarching objective is to provide evidence that the capacity to devise an effective marketing plan is primarily predicated on having a comprehensive grasp of the decision-making processes that customers carry out. When it comes to marketing, wanting to accomplish one without knowing the other will only lead to disastrous results.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Acknowledgement: The author would like to acknowledge and thank his supervisor, Prof Zhang Qi from Economics Department of China University of Geosciences (CUG), Wuhan, China for overseeing the paper and special appreciation to China Scholarship Council (CSC) for granting scholarship to study at China University of Geosciences (CUG), Wuhan, China

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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